

MODERN VIEWS OF ARTISTIC PUBLICIST ESSAYS

Iroda Nasimova

Uzbekistan is journalism and mass
Communications University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5559634>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 01st October 2021
Accepted: 05th October 2021
Online: 10th October 2021

KEY WORDS

*literary, philosophical,
historical, biographical*

ABSTRACT

In this article, in this article, the importance of the artist, our national publications, is analyzed the philosophical essences of the decorative artists. In particular, a talks talked about Shukur Kholmiraev, Nosirjon Juraev and Shodmani Gre'd.

The Essi artistic publicist genre also cannot be imagined without the elements "artistic". He serves to show the attention of the attention of the work of perfection not only in the global Esenavis, a unique, philosophical, historical, religious and literary-critical and memorable direction.

The criteria of point of activity Author of the essos of the essays that are unconsecutored with high creative skills can be recognized by Shukur Kholmiraev. The weight of the artist essays in this genre and the artist essays in this genre are heavy in our literary creation and clusiness.

Sh.Kholmiraev created the memories of new forms in the Uzbek memory, applying for the landscape to represent the elements of the artistic. Because the Essecon image is similar to the psyche of landscapes, which recalls the imagination, the figurative expression, such as the epic species. First of all, the image of

the landscape is aimed at revealing the mood of the heroes in the essay. "The trees in front of the bulls were a thicker Saul, as if not, the side of the breeze, and Goho-Goho, were cute.

While this tradition continues in a decent, new generation writers are also available to the finger. For example, the gammark can be accepted as the essentials of "Posistry Dividi" published through the newspaper and a number of Internet sites "Uzbekistan literature" (Uzas, 2013 / We want to address the Essan to the "way to the monumentation of the heart".

"You'll get away. Cavalry or yayov. The grass in the spring pressed on fire and finds a mistake of the missing trails. TAKES ENTERPRISE, PAID. When you get a foot-to-fly, you will ride on the horse again. The rocks, springs, springs, wild animals, like giants that have put themselves in sleep. The brown channel that bries the "Pir". You

pull you down ... "You will strive to get to a mysterious address.

Essada elements of the prose and musical are the elements of prose, prosecution of the essay - is one of the most important signs of artistic. In particular, music is not just a music, sometimes mistaken and find, "Finding", "Rooms, Wild Boddoms". ESS is thus attracting the reader himself and once moves to go to:

"There is no other" unselfish in Bukhotag ". There are some of these address as a common sulfate, sanctuary, and prosperous graves based on the sanctuary, the status of the status of the status of the status of the status. There are also specific aspects of this position, which is a two-day route from the nearest population, saying that "no-wrong" is still duties. "

As protested as a bright sign of artist above, the art of the landscapes is a question of rock in Babelat. The rock shows that the face of the rock is very slowly and describing it as "tears," as "tears or not water or" tears, "they are using the art of making it effective.

"Of course, drinking from this water that brings for just a small bucket is lucky. Or it may also have been drinking who the nose is drinking, ten or ten days-twenty days. Interestingly, it is said that it does not drink from the water. And this event is mentioned in gurungs as a news. "

Well, a word about the fact that during the Essia, the word is a good likeness and goes on a goal: "I think it is a symbol, understanding, understanding, Mozmillis seem. And I think this system symbolizes is the way to literature, literature. That is, the distance from the Bobotaph of the sun is from the Bobotagog Collection of the first bladder to Tashkent, "I don't even seem to me to be a journey."

It is actually about to overcome the hardships of ways and creation in literature and that this goal is to have a chance, or to have a place to have someone.

Essi next lines are also given: "... You see the flap of Cholpon, Osman Nasir, Ertbek, and Oybek, Erkin Vahidov, or Osman not even if you can give hand, even if you can give hand. Shavkat Mahran, which is the head of the publishing house where the publishing house has taken, is in fact me and I have not "any other".

Esses did not have full content with the high expression of the bad thing. It features an essay "position, and the facts and opinions.

In fact, he is concerned about the face of reading and creativity in society, "Hey friends knows something - I do not know what we believe in us, our professionalism. But I'm not saying. Because these questions are not answered in myself. I have heard that five hundred verses could not be held discipleship in the artist of Gaza."

The discussion of the Stories in the essay of the Essun still is between the people queuing water in the Boysun and places themselves and the essay in the following point: "But we are still on the verge." Entertainment Obidaci Cario is on the roadsides. And the road is long, mysterious, a dry. You will leave, in a horse or a foot. "

In this essay drawing up the landscape, as well drawing, as well as contacting the mind and a goal, it shows how sharpness of the shammel hello. Taking a portrait in the essay also serves to increase its artistic value.

But now the approach selected to the study is a little different. The Portrait of the hero is not in the form of "legendary", "unique" man, but in appearance. We bring

an essay article "Namromat" or Osman, who did not miss me "or the" frame ":

"Osman does not deceive the heart. His poems do not give a person rest, does not push the pond of grief, it does not calm the heart. It cannot be read to relax what they write. On the contrary, he disgraces the leisure, breaks the rest, puts a hanging to the heart. Sleeping is slapping two hundred people. The dusty appearance stuck in the light of the new coat and then leads to the hemisphere, even though he crumbles to your shoulder."

The tenderness in describing the portrait:

"Osman does not deceive the heart. He does not try to infect a pain he does not feel. Doesn't explain the pain in which he cuts his finger without cutting his finger. If the tooth hurts or defeat, immediately, it will not immediately impose Ayyohannos about death. Coline writes that it is so made so much about toothache, that you involuntarily said, "It was better to die than that!" You start thinkin"

The man who recites an Essian article is not about Burtattkesar, but about the image of the hero of hero, vice versa. Especially after reading a new poem manuscript of Osman, the following figures are embodied in the eyes of:

"I saw the manuscript, and in my mind, first of all, no one, who recognizes nothing, not recognizing anything; Usmon

Azimov, who wished an ethnic surrounding somnap in Tashkent, long-miss; It is then the heart of readers at the speed of light, the word of the word is Osman, whom he knew the poem's holy in the status of poem; In the end, Osmon, the Master Osmon, which meant the burden of literature, is placed on one side of the seventice-year lives. And I felt that these four appearances are the respect of both men and others. "

Esse began unusually, and in this way, i.e. without changes in the above image:

There is a similar essential articles of talented adib Nosirjon Juraev. In particular, dedicated to the 2012 essays, "The value of youth", "Dr. Beer's grief", "Why the eyes of the People's Pair of Uzbekistan" is a newspaper of Uzbekistan Literature and Arts 2012 is one of the number of year.

Today, mostly most of the essays written on socio-political, enlighten topics are far from the elements of the artist, and are declared to the reader as possible. However, it should be noted that the beautiful creative, which will never, never weigh, but its opinion increases, but the views of his views. True, the publicist work should pay attention to any issue, to think of something, to solve a problem, but does not mean any genre arises if it expresses the idea. Therefore, we did not divide the essay of objective essay in objective and subjective lighting types.

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